

ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSROOM ANXIETY AND ENGAGEMENT OF STUDENTS IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR ENHANCEMENT

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English Language Classroom Anxiety and Engagement of Students in Relation to Academic Performance: Basis for Enhancement

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Abstract

The study of Soriano & Co (2022) emphasizes the global significance of English proficiency, setting the stage for a nuanced investigation into the interrelation between English language anxiety, engagement, and academic performance. This study examined the relationship between student classroom engagement, English language anxiety, and academic performance among Grade 11 and Grade 12 students in a public secondary school during the 2023-2024 academic year. Using a quantitative descriptive-correlational design, 134 students were selected through stratified random sampling. Data were gathered using adapted questionnaires on English language anxiety and engagement, alongside academic records. Most of the respondents were male and from families earning less than Php 9,100.00 per month. Most students had parents who were high school graduates. The study found high levels of engagement with a mean score of 3.73, particularly in behavioral engagement with a mean score of 3.58. Anxiety levels were moderate with a mean score of 3.51 and fear of judgment with a mean score of 3.58 being the highest. No significant differences in engagement, anxiety, or academic performance were observed based on sex, parents' educational attainment, or family income. A significant negative correlation was found between anxiety and engagement ($r = -0.24, p < 0.005$), indicating that higher anxiety is associated with lower engagement. A significant positive correlation was found between engagement and academic performance ($G = 0.44, p < 0.001$), suggesting that higher engagement leads to better academic outcomes. No significant relationship was found between anxiety and academic performance ($r = -0.02, p > 0.889$). These findings highlight the importance of enhancing student engagement and addressing anxiety to improve academic performance.

Keywords: *academic performance, enhancement program, level of engagement, level of english language anxiety, test anxiety*

Introduction

The importance of English proficiency is widely acknowledged (Soriano & Co, 2022) studies emphasize the global significance of English proficiency, setting the stage for a nuanced investigation into the interrelation between English language anxiety, engagement, and academic performance.

Moreover, the Philippines recognizes the critical role of English proficiency in its education system, as evidenced by research from Desta (2019) focusing on learners' degree of engagement. The study builds upon this national context, investigating how English language anxiety and engagement interact within the unique Philippine educational framework.

Rohliah et al.'s (2023) work expands on the concept of English language anxiety, providing insights into how cultural and contextual factors may influence language learning experiences. This regional perspective enriches the study by shedding light on the complexities faced by Filipino learners in English language learning.

To contribute to the existing body of knowledge, this study aims to explore the interplay between these factors on an international, national, regional, and local scale, providing a comprehensive understanding of the complex dynamics shaping learners' language learning experiences. While existing studies have highlighted the global significance of English proficiency, there is a gap in understanding the specific challenges faced by Filipino learners within their unique educational context.

Many learners struggle with fears like speaking in public, understanding English, and feeling insecure about their language abilities. Using surveys and analyzing academic data, the study examined these challenges and find ways to help learners overcome them, ultimately improving their English proficiency and academic success. This study aimed to explore how learners' anxiety about English affects their involvement in language activities and their academic performance in a particular senior high school during the academic year 2023-2024.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of senior high school learners' English language classroom anxiety, level engagement and academic performance in Raymundo T. Tongson National High School, Su-ay Extension, Division of Himamaylan for SY 2023-2024. Specifically, this study sought answers for the following research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the senior high school learner respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. educational attainment of parents; and

- 1.3. family income?
2. What is the level of senior high school learners' classroom engagement when taken as a whole and when grouped according to:
 - 2.1. behavioral;
 - 2.2. cognitive; and
 - 2.3. emotional?
3. What is the level of English language anxiety of senior high school learners' when taken as a whole and when grouped according to:
 - 3.1. communication;
 - 3.2. fear of judgement; and
 - 3.3. test anxiety?
4. What is the level of senior high school learners' academic performance when taken as a whole and when grouped according to:
 - 4.1. sex;
 - 4.2. educational attainment of parents; and
 - 4.3. family income?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of senior high school learners' engagement when grouped according to:
 - 5.1. sex;
 - 5.2. educational attainment of parents; and
 - 5.3. family income?
6. Is there a significant difference in the level of senior high school learners' English language classroom anxiety when grouped according to:
 - 6.1. sex;
 - 6.2. educational attainment of parents; and
 - 6.3. family income?
7. Is there a significant difference in the level of learners' academic performance when grouped according to:
 - 7.1. sex;
 - 7.2. educational attainment of parents; and
 - 7.3. family income?
8. Is there a significant relationship between the classroom engagement and level of English language anxiety of senior high school learners?
9. Is there a significant relationship between the level of engagement and academic performance of senior high school learners?
10. Is there a significant relationship between the English language anxiety and academic performance of senior high school learners?

Literature Review

The high levels of engagement across all dimensions suggest that current educational practices are effective in fostering learner involvement and commitment. To maintain and further enhance this engagement, educators should continue to develop strategies that integrate all three dimensions of engagement. For example, incorporating interactive and thought-provoking activities can sustain cognitive engagement, while fostering a supportive and inclusive school environment can enhance emotional engagement. Additionally, providing learners with opportunities for active participation in class and extracurricular activities can boost behavioral engagement. Schools should also focus on professional development for teachers to equip them with skills to sustain high engagement levels and ensure that the curriculum remains challenging and relevant to learners' interests and future goals. These measures can help sustain and further improve learner engagement, leading to better educational outcomes.

Halif et al. (2020) highlight the importance of integrating behavioral, cognitive, and emotional dimensions to enhance overall learner engagement. Similarly, Teng and Wang (2024) emphasize the role of school context and achievement motivation in promoting learner engagement, supporting the finding that high engagement levels are indicative of effective educational practices.

However, some studies suggest variability in engagement levels based on external factors. Tenga and Wang (2024) found that engagement levels can significantly vary based on socioeconomic status and school environment, which might deviate from the consistently high engagement levels observed in this study.

Research on language anxiety, which often highlights communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and test anxiety as key components of language learning anxiety (Mahmoud and Jassim, 2023).

Kuhon (2020) highlights the influence of parental education and family income on child achievement, emphasizing the indirect role of parental expectations and the home environment. Similarly, Mauliya et al. (2020) conducts a meta-analytic review of research on socioeconomic status and academic achievement, affirming the association between family background and educational outcomes. Bilal et al. (2022) also explore the socioeconomic status and academic achievement trajectories from childhood to adolescence,

shedding light on the complex interplay between socioeconomic factors and educational outcomes.

An existing research that finds minimal differences in engagement levels between sexes, suggesting that factors such as teaching methods, classroom environment, and individual learner interests might play more significant roles in influencing learner engagement (Kong, 2021).

Nevertheless, some studies suggest that while overall engagement levels might not differ significantly by sex, the types of engagement might vary. For example, females might exhibit higher emotional and behavioral engagement, while males might show higher cognitive engagement in certain contexts (Yan, 2021). Therefore, while the overall levels are similar, educators might still consider diverse engagement strategies that cater to different types of engagement preferences across genders.

Learner engagement is influenced more by factors such as individual learner characteristics, classroom environment, and teacher-learner interactions rather than parental education (Subramaniam & Muniandy, 2019). In contradictory to this, some studies suggest that while overall engagement levels may not differ significantly by parental education, the nature of parental support and involvement, which often correlates with higher educational attainment, can influence different aspects of learner engagement. For instance, parents with higher educational attainment might be more equipped to provide academic support and resources, thereby indirectly enhancing learner engagement (Hoi, 2023).

The results of the study conducted by Ahamed et al. (2022) shows that while socioeconomic status can influence overall educational opportunities and outcomes, its direct impact on engagement levels is not significant.

On the other hand, some studies suggest that socioeconomic factors can indirectly affect learner engagement through the availability of educational resources and parental support. Higher-income families might afford more educational materials and extracurricular support, which can enhance learner engagement. Additionally, family stability and access to resources, often linked to income, might influence learners' overall well-being and indirectly impact their engagement in school (Portela, 2020).

Some studies indicate that while anxiety levels might be similar, the emotional experiences of males and females in language learning can differ, suggesting that anxiety interventions might still benefit from gender-specific adjustments (Pristiyaputri et al., 2023). Additionally, context-specific differences in anxiety levels between genders have been noted, implying that other factors might influence anxiety in different educational settings (Hughes, 2020).

Language anxiety is influenced more by personal and situational factors rather than by parental background (Baş & Özcan, 2018). Moreover, some studies suggest that parental involvement and support, which often correlate with higher educational attainment, can impact learner anxiety and overall academic performance, indicating that while direct anxiety levels may not differ significantly, the broader academic support environment could still play a role (Jamshed et al., 2024). Additionally, the overall home environment and parental attitudes towards education, which are often shaped by their educational experiences, can influence learner attitudes and anxiety indirectly (Soares & Woods, 2020).

While socioeconomic status can influence overall educational opportunities and outcomes, its direct impact on language anxiety is not significant (Abu et al., 2021). However, some studies suggest that socioeconomic factors can indirectly affect learner anxiety levels through the availability of educational resources and parental support. For instance, higher-income families might afford more educational materials and extracurricular support, which can reduce overall stress and anxiety. Additionally, the broader context of family stability and access to resources, which are often linked to income, might influence learners' overall well-being and indirectly impact their classroom anxiety (Baş & Özcan, 2018).

Gender differences in academic performance are often minimal when other variables, such as socio-economic status and school environment, are controlled (Kuhon, 2020). On the other hand, the study of Mauliya et al. (2020) suggest that while overall academic performance might not differ significantly by gender, the subjects or areas of study in which learners excel may vary. For example, females often perform better in language arts, while males might excel in mathematics and science, reflecting different academic strengths and learning preferences.

De la Fuente-Mella et al. (2022) claimed on their research that while parental education can influence academic outcomes, its direct impact on academic performance is often mediated by other factors such as parental involvement and socio-economic status. In opposition, parental educational attainment can indirectly affect learner performance through the quality and quantity of academic support provided at home. Parents with higher educational attainment might have more resources and knowledge to assist with homework and educational activities, potentially enhancing learner performance (Arroyo-Barrigüete et al., 2022).

Another research shows that, although socioeconomic status can affect overall educational opportunities and outcomes, when other factors like the school environment and unique learner characteristics are taken into account, its direct impact on academic performance may not be significant (Bhatt & Sarangi, 2019). Some studies suggest that socioeconomic factors can indirectly affect learner performance through the availability of educational resources and parental support. For example, higher-income families might afford more educational materials and extracurricular support, potentially enhancing learner performance. Additionally, family stability and access to resources, often linked to income, might influence learners' overall well-being and indirectly impact their academic performance (Bilal et al., 2022).

Effective strategies may include creating a supportive and inclusive classroom environment, offering anxiety-reducing techniques such as mindfulness and stress management workshops, and providing positive feedback and encouragement (Feng & Hong, 2022). Additionally, this significant relationship highlights the need for targeted interventions that specifically address language anxiety to improve learner engagement. By reducing anxiety, educators can help learners feel more comfortable and confident, thereby increasing their participation and investment in learning activities. These results align with research suggesting that reducing classroom anxiety can lead to higher levels of engagement and better academic outcomes (Wang et al., 2023).

Cui and Wang (2024) highlighted the need to foster and maintain high levels of learner engagement to enhance academic achievement. Given the significant relationship between engagement and academic performance, educators should focus on strategies that promote active participation, interest, and emotional investment in learning. Creating an engaging and interactive classroom environment, incorporating diverse teaching methods, and providing opportunities for learner collaboration can help boost engagement levels. Additionally, addressing factors that may hinder engagement, such as classroom anxiety or lack of resources, can further support academic success (Nsenga, 2022).

The study of Alaofi and Russell (2022) showed that English language classroom anxiety does not significantly impact the academic performance of senior high school learners. Learners' levels of anxiety in the English language classroom appear to have little to no correlation with their academic performance, meaning that high anxiety levels do not necessarily predict lower academic outcomes and vice versa. This indicates that other factors may play a more significant role in determining academic success, such as individual resilience, study habits, and external support systems

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to explore the intricate relationships among key variables in the investigation. The descriptive component of the research design involved the comprehensive description and analysis of the current status and characteristics of English language anxiety, level of engagement, and academic performance among learners in the specified grade level. Surveys were administered to collect self-reported data on learners' perceived anxiety levels, engagement in language-related activities, and academic performance. The correlational aspect of the research design aimed to examine the relationships between variables. Specifically, the study seeks to correlate English language anxiety with academic performance and level of engagement.

This research design is particularly well-suited for investigating the complex interplay between English language anxiety, level of engagement, and academic performance. It allows for the identification of potential correlations without manipulating variables, offering insights into the natural associations within the existing educational context (Panda, 2022).

Respondents

Learners enrolled in Grades 11 to 12 in the academic year 2023-2024 were the primary respondents of this study. To ensure homogeneity in the sample, the study concentrated on this single grade level, allowing for a targeted analysis of language acquisition experiences within a specific educational context. Using Yamane's Formula, a sample of 134 senior high school learners were taken from the population of 201.

To ensure representation from multiple classes within the required grade level, a stratified random selection approach was used. Stratification allows for the examination of potential differences across multiple classes, resulting in a more complete understanding of the subject group.

Instrument

An adopted and revised questionnaires on the level of English language anxiety and level of engagement was employed in this investigation. It is a standardized instrument, but it was revised to suit the needs of the Filipino respondents. The instrument was adopted from the study of Hidayati (2018) for the level of English language anxiety while for their level of engagement a researcher-made was utilized. There were three sections to the questionnaire. Part 1 contained queries on respondents' profiles such as age, sex, length of service and educational attainment.

Part 2 was the questionnaire for learners' level of engagement with 30 questions divided among different components specifically behavioral engagement of learners with 10 questions, cognitive engagement of learners composed of 10 questions and emotional engagement of learners with 10 questions. The respondents were asked to rate each item using the five-point Likert scale for their level of engagement which contains the following scores of means with their corresponding descriptions: 5; always, 4; often, 3; sometimes, 2; rarely, and 1 almost never.

Part 3 of the instrument is the questionnaire for learners' level of English language anxiety. The original questionnaire was composed of 33 items divided into specific components which includes communication apprehension, fear of evaluation by peers and teachers and test anxiety. The researcher added 7 items distributed among the three components making a total of 40 items. To quantify these

subjective experiences, a Likert scale is utilized, offering respondents a range of responses from 1 to 5, each with distinct descriptors. A rating of 5, "Strongly Agree," indicates a robust endorsement of the provided statement, reflecting a high level of agreement. The "Agree" option, with a rating of 4, signifies a positive inclination towards the statement without the same intensity as the highest endorsement. Positioned at 3, "Neither Agree nor Disagree" serves as a neutral response for participants who feel ambivalent or neutral towards the statement. Conversely, a rating of 2, "Disagree," indicates a negative response, showing that the respondent does not align with the statement, though the disagreement is not as strong as it could be. Finally, the lowest rating of 1, "Strongly Disagree," represents a strong rejection of the statement, denoting a high level of disagreement and opposition to the idea or proposition presented. This scale provides a nuanced method for capturing the range of respondents' attitudes and feelings, facilitating a detailed analysis of subjective experiences.

Moreover, the pupils' academic performance was interpreted as follows: 90 to 100; outstanding, 85 to 89; very satisfactory, 80 to 84; satisfactory, 75 to 79; satisfactory, and lastly 74 and below; did not meet expectations.

The instruments were subjected to a jury validation process involving three experts in language education and psychological measurement, ensuring their relevance and cultural appropriateness for the local context. Using the validity tool developed by Good and Scates through jury validation, a rating of 4.70 for the instrument for learners' language anxiety while the level of engagement instrument received a rating of 4.78 which were both interpreted as very good.

For reliability, the researcher conducted pilot testing of the instrument to the senior high school learners at a neighboring school and employed Cronbach's alpha, a widely accepted measure of internal consistency. The reliability index of the two standardized instruments was 0.903 for language anxiety instrument and 0.932 for the level of engagement respectively which means that both instruments were highly reliable.

Procedure

The data gathering procedure for this study entails a meticulous process, starting with the acquisition of necessary permits and culminating in the completion of the research paper. The initial step involves securing permits and approvals from relevant authorities, such as the graduate school office, division superintendent and school administrator to conduct the study ethically and within institutional guidelines.

After obtaining ethical clearance and informed consent from participants and their parents or guardians, the survey was administered to selected respondents through a stratified random sampling technique. The structured survey comprises three sections, capturing respondents' profiles, level of engagement, and English language anxiety. The respondents utilized a five-point Likert scale to rate each item, providing insights into their experiences.

Simultaneously, academic performance data were collected from official records, aligning with a standardized grading system widely recognized in educational contexts. To ensure data accuracy and integrity, collected information undergoes a meticulous verification and cross-checking process.

The final step involved the synthesis and interpretation of results, culminating in the completion of the research paper. The detailed process, from acquiring permits to the conclusion of the research paper, underscored the study's commitment to methodological rigor, ethical considerations, and the generation of valuable insights into language education and learner dynamics within the specified grade level and educational context.

Data Analysis

The data collection phase, statistical analysis, including correlation analysis and descriptive statistics, were applied to interpret the relationships and patterns within the dataset. The findings contributed to a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics between English language anxiety, level of engagement, and academic performance.

For the demographic profile of the senior high school learner respondents, frequency and percentage were used to describe sex, educational attainment of parents, and family income.

To determine the level of English language classroom anxiety among senior high school learners, the mean was used for overall anxiety and for specific categories such as communication, fear of judgment, and test anxiety. The mean is used to measure central tendency, giving an average level of anxiety for the entire group and for each specific type of anxiety.

Similarly, the level of engagement among senior high school learners was assessed using the mean for overall engagement and for specific dimensions such as behavioral, cognitive, and emotional engagement. The mean provides a clear indication of the average level of engagement across these dimensions.

The level of academic performance among senior high school learners was also analyzed using the mean for the overall group and for subgroups based on sex, educational attainment of parents, and family income. The mean allows for comparison of average academic performance across these different groups.

To determine if there were significant differences in the level of English language classroom anxiety, the t-test was used for

comparisons based on sex, and ANOVA was used for comparisons based on educational attainment of parents and family income. The t-test is suitable for comparing the means between two groups, while ANOVA is used to compare the means among three or more groups.

Similarly, the t-test was used to examine differences in engagement based on sex, and ANOVA was used for educational attainment of parents and family income. These tests help to determine if there are statistically significant differences in engagement levels across these groups.

For academic performance, the Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare differences based on sex, while the Kruskal-Wallis test was used for comparisons based on educational attainment of parents and family income. These non-parametric tests are appropriate when the data do not necessarily follow a normal distribution.

To examine the relationships between variables, Pearson r was used to assess the relationship between English language classroom anxiety and engagement. Pearson r measures the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two continuous variables. The Gamma coefficient was used to examine the relationship between English language classroom anxiety and academic performance, and between engagement and academic performance. The Gamma coefficient is suitable for ordinal data and helps to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between two ranked variables.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher strongly committed to ethical standards by prioritizing respondent confidentiality and data privacy. Access to survey data was strictly limited to the researcher and thesis adviser, ensuring sensitive information remained secure. Respondents' names were also deliberately omitted from the final report to maintain anonymity. This approach highlights the researcher's dedication to upholding ethical research practices, safeguarding participant identities, and fostering a trustworthy research environment. Such measures underscore the importance of respecting and protecting the rights and privacy of all participants involved.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The table below shows the proportional allocation of the respondents of the study.

Table 1. *Profile of the Senior High School Learner Respondents according to Sex, Grade Level & Educational Attainment of Parents*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Sex	Female	61	45.5
	Male	73	54.5
	Total	134	100
Education	Elementary Graduate	41	30.6
	High School Graduate	82	61.2
	College Graduate	11	8.2
	Total	134	100
Family Income	Php. 63,700 to Php. 109,200 per Month	1	0.7
	Php. 36,400 to Php. 63,700 per Month	1	0.7
	Php. 18,200 to Php. 36,400 per Month	6	4.5
	Php. 9,100 to Php. 18,200.00 per Month	37	27.6
	Less than Php. 9,100.00 per Month	89	66.4
	Total	134	100

Table 1 outlines the demographic profile of senior high school learner respondents, focusing on sex, grade level, and the educational attainment of their parents. The respondents consist of 61 females (45.5%) and 73 males (54.5%), indicating a slightly higher number of male learners. In terms of the educational background of the parents, a majority have completed high school, accounting for 61.2% (82 parents), followed by 30.6% (41 parents) who are elementary graduates, and a small percentage of 8.2% (11 parents) who have completed college.

Family income levels among the respondents show a significant concentration in the lower-income bracket. A substantial 66.4% (89 families) earn less than Php. 9,100.00 per month. The next income bracket, Php. 9,100 to Php. 18,200.00 per month, includes 27.6% (37 families) of the respondents. Only a small fraction of families fall into higher income brackets, with 4.5% (6 families) earning between Php. 18,200 and Php. 36,400, and a negligible 0.7% (1 family each) earning between Php. 36,400 and Php. 63,700, and Php. 63,700 and Php. 109,200.

Level of Senior High School Learners' Engagement when taken as a whole and when grouped according to Domains

This study explores learners' overall engagement levels by breaking them down into behavioral, cognitive, and emotional domains. A

summary of various engagement levels is provided in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Level of Senior High School Learners' Engagement when taken as a whole and when grouped according to Behavioral, Cognitive & Emotional

Level of Engagement	n	Mean	Interpretation
Behavioral	134	3.77	High
Cognitive	134	3.69	High
Emotional	134	3.74	High
As a whole	134	3.73	High

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Very High; 3.40-4.19, High; 2.60-3.39, Moderate; 1.80-2.59, Low; 1.00-1.79, Very Low

Table 2 presents the levels of engagement among senior high school learners, measured across different dimensions: behavioral, cognitive, and emotional. Each dimension was evaluated, and the results were aggregated to provide an overall engagement level.

The mean engagement level for behavioral engagement is 3.77, indicating a relatively high level of learner participation in activities such as attending classes, completing assignments, and adhering to school rules. This suggests that learners are generally active and involved in their educational tasks and classroom routines.

For cognitive engagement, the mean score is slightly lower at 3.69. This dimension reflects learners' investment in learning, their desire to understand complex ideas, and their effort in thinking critically. The high mean score suggests that learners are intellectually engaged and motivated to learn, though there might be slight variations in the depth of cognitive engagement compared to behavioral engagement.

The emotional engagement level, with a mean score of 3.74, indicates a strong emotional connection to the school environment, including feelings of interest, happiness, and belonging. This level of emotional engagement shows that learners generally feel positive about their school experiences and are emotionally invested in their education.

When the engagement levels are taken as a whole, the mean score is 3.73. This aggregate score shows that overall, senior high school learners exhibit a high level of engagement across behavioral, cognitive, and emotional dimensions.

These findings have important propositions for educators and school administrators. The high levels of engagement across all dimensions suggest that current educational practices are effective in fostering learner involvement and commitment. To maintain and further enhance this engagement, educators should continue to develop strategies that integrate all three dimensions of engagement. For example, incorporating interactive and thought-provoking activities can sustain cognitive engagement, while fostering a supportive and inclusive school environment can enhance emotional engagement. Additionally, providing learners with opportunities for active participation in class and extracurricular activities can boost behavioral engagement. Schools should also focus on professional development for teachers to equip them with skills to sustain high engagement levels and ensure that the curriculum remains challenging and relevant to learners' interests and future goals. These measures can help sustain and further improve learner engagement, leading to better educational outcomes.

Level of English Language Classroom Anxiety of Senior High School Learners' when taken as a whole and when grouped according to Domains

Understanding learner anxiety in English language classrooms is important for improving educational outcomes. This analysis examines the overall anxiety levels of senior high school learners and breaks them down into specific domains: communication apprehension, fear of judgment, and test anxiety. The table below provides a detailed overview of these anxiety levels.

Table 3 Level of English Language Classroom Anxiety of Senior High School Learners' when taken as a whole and when grouped according to Communication, Fear of Judgement & Test Anxiety

Level of English Language Classroom Anxiety	n	Mean	Interpretation
Communication	134	3.49	High
Fear of Judgement	134	3.58	High
Test Anxiety	134	3.48	High
As a whole	134	3.51	High

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Very High; 3.40-4.19, High; 2.60-3.39, Moderate; 1.80-2.59, Low; 1.00-1.79, Very Low

Table 3 presents that the mean of anxiety for communication is 3.49, indicating a moderate level of anxiety when learners are required to use English to communicate. This suggests that learners experience some apprehension and nervousness in situations that require speaking or interacting in English.

When considering fear of judgment, the mean score is slightly higher at 3.58. This dimension reflects learners' anxiety about being judged by peers, teachers, or themselves when using English. The slightly elevated mean suggests that this is a significant source of anxiety, perhaps due to concerns about making mistakes and being evaluated negatively.

Further, for test anxiety, the mean score is 3.48, similar to the communication anxiety level. This indicates that learners experience moderate anxiety during English language assessments, which could affect their performance due to stress and fear of failing.

When the anxiety levels are taken as a whole, the mean score is 3.51. This aggregate score shows that overall, senior high school learners experience a moderate level of anxiety in their English language classrooms, encompassing communication, fear of judgment, and test-related stress.

The findings indicate a moderate level of English language classroom anxiety among senior high school learners, with slightly higher anxiety related to fear of judgment. These results suggest that educators should prioritize creating a supportive and non-judgmental classroom environment, employing anxiety-reducing strategies such as positive reinforcement and collaborative activities. Curriculum developers should integrate confidence-building exercises, while assessment methods could be diversified to include low-stakes evaluations to mitigate test anxiety. Additionally, teacher training programs should incorporate techniques for recognizing and addressing language anxiety, and schools should provide support services like counseling and stress management workshops to help learners manage their anxiety effectively. These measures can collectively enhance learners' language learning experiences and outcomes.

Level of Senior High School Learners' Academic Performance when taken as a whole and when grouped according to Profile Variables

Examining the academic performance of senior high school learners offers insights crucial for educational planning and support. This analysis evaluates overall academic performance and further dissects it based on profile variables such as sex, educational attainment of parents, and family income. The table below offers a concise summary of learners' academic performance.

Table 4. *Level of Senior High School Learners' Academic Performance when taken as a whole and when grouped according to Sex, Educational Attainment of Parents, and Family Income*

Profile	Category	n	Mean	Interpretation
Sex	Female	61	89.97	Very Satisfactory
	Male	73	90.71	Outstanding
Education	Elementary Graduate	41	90.05	Outstanding
	High School Graduate	82	90.28	Outstanding
	College Graduate	11	92.27	Outstanding
Family Income	Php. 63,700 to Php. 109,200 per Month	1	97.00	Upper Middle Inc
	Php. 36,400 to Php. 63,700 per Month	1	90.00	Middle Class
	Php. 18,200 to Php. 36,400 per Month	6	89.67	Lower Middle Income
	Php. 9,100 to Php. 18,200.00 per Month	37	89.70	Low Income (but not poor)
	Less than Php. 9,100.00 per Month	89	90.63	Poor
As a whole		134	90.37	Outstanding

Among females, the mean score is 89.97, interpreted as "Very Satisfactory," while for males, it is 90.71, indicating "Outstanding" performance. Regarding the educational attainment of parents, learners with college graduate parents achieved the highest mean score of 92.27, interpreted as "Outstanding," followed by those with high school graduate parents with a mean score of 90.28, also categorized as "Outstanding." Learners with parents who are elementary graduates scored slightly lower but still outstandingly, with a mean of 90.05. In terms of family income, learners from families earning less than Php. 9,100.00 per month achieved a mean score of 90.63, labeled as "Outstanding," while those from families earning between Php. 9,100 to Php. 18,200.00 per month scored a mean of 89.70, classified as "Very Satisfactory." Similarly, those from families earning between Php. 18,200 to Php. 36,400 per month also scored a mean of 89.67, interpreted as "Very Satisfactory." Only one learner each from families earning between Php. 36,400 to Php. 63,700 and Php. 63,700 to Php. 109,200 per month was included, with mean scores of 90.00 and 97.00, respectively, both categorized as "Outstanding." Overall, when considering academic performance as a whole, the mean score is 90.37, classified as "Outstanding."

These findings imply that learners' academic performance is generally high across different demographic categories. However, certain factors such as parental education and family income demonstrate some influence on performance levels. Learners with college graduate parents tend to perform slightly better than those with lower parental education levels, indicating the potential impact of parental education on academic outcomes. Additionally, learners from higher-income families tend to perform better on average, though there are exceptions. These findings underscore the importance of providing support and resources to learners from lower-income families to ensure equitable academic opportunities. Furthermore, educators and policymakers should consider implementing interventions that address potential barriers to academic success, such as providing additional support for learners from lower socioeconomic backgrounds.

Difference in the Level of Senior High School Learners' Classroom Engagement when grouped according to Profile

This research also examined the difference in the respondents' level of engagement across the varying profile variables. The succeeding discussion focuses on the differences in learner engagement when grouped by sex, educational attainment of parents and family income. The table below provide a detailed comparison of these engagement levels.

Table 5.1. Difference in the Level of Senior High School Learners' Engagement when grouped according to Sex

<i>Sex</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Female	61	2.05
Male	73	2.12

Computed Value (t): -0.62

P-value: 0.537

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table examines the difference in the level of engagement among senior high school learners when grouped according to sex. The mean engagement level for female learners is 2.05, while for male learners, it is slightly higher at 2.12. The computed t-value for this difference is -0.62, and the p-value is 0.537. Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis (Ho). This indicates that there is no significant difference in the levels of engagement between male and female learners.

These findings of the present study suggest that sex does not significantly impact the level of engagement among senior high school learners. Both male and female learners exhibit similar levels of engagement in their educational activities, indicating that engagement strategies can be uniformly applied across genders without needing to tailor them specifically for males or females. This uniformity simplifies the design and implementation of engagement-enhancing interventions, ensuring they are equally effective for all learners.

Table 5.2. Difference in the Level of Senior High School Learners' Engagement when grouped according to Educational Attainment of Parents

<i>Educational Attainment of Parents</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Elementary Graduate	41	3.73
High School Graduate	82	3.73
College Graduate	11	3.77

Computed Value (F): 0.95

P-value: 0.593

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 5.2 examines the difference in the level of engagement among senior high school learners when grouped according to the educational attainment of their parents. The mean engagement level for learners with parents who are elementary graduates is 3.73. Those with parents who are high school graduates also have a mean level of 3.73. Learners with college graduate parents have a slightly higher mean level of 3.77. The computed F-value for this difference is 0.95, and the p-value is 0.593. Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis (Ho). This indicates that there is no significant difference in the levels of engagement among learners based on the educational attainment of their parents.

These findings imply that the educational attainment of parents does not significantly impact the level of engagement among senior high school learners. Regardless of whether parents have completed elementary, high school, or college education, learners exhibit similar levels of engagement in their educational activities. This implies that engagement strategies can be broadly applied to learners without needing to tailor them specifically based on parental education levels.

Table 5.3. Difference in the Level of Senior High School Learners' Engagement when Grouped according to Family Income

<i>Family Income</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Php. 63,700 to Php. 109,200 per Month	1	3.87
Php. 36,400 to Php. 63,700 per Month	1	3.97
Php. 18,200 to Php. 36,400 per Month	6	3.49
Php. 9,100 to Php. 18,200.00 per Month	37	3.88
Less than Php. 9,100.00 per Month	89	3.68

Computed Value (F): 0.73

P-value: 0.903

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The following discussion focuses on the difference in the level of engagement among senior high school learners when grouped according to family income. Learners from families earning less than Php. 9,100.00 per month have a mean engagement level of 3.68. Those with family incomes between Php. 9,100 to Php. 18,200.00 per month have a higher mean level of 3.88. For learners from families earning between Php. 18,200 to Php. 36,400 per month, the mean engagement level is 3.49. The mean level for those from families with an income of Php. 36,400 to Php. 63,700 per month is 3.97, and for the highest income group (Php. 63,700 to Php. 109,200 per month), the mean engagement level is 3.87. The computed F-value for this difference is 0.73, and the p-value is 0.903. Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis (Ho). This indicates that there is no significant difference in the levels of engagement among learners based on family income.

These results of the study indicate that family income does not significantly impact the level of engagement among senior high school

learners. Regardless of income level, learners exhibit similar levels of engagement in their educational activities.

Difference in the Level of Senior High School Learners' English Language Anxiety when grouped according to Profile

Analyzing the variations in English language classroom anxiety among senior high school learners based on different profiles is crucial for developing effective support strategies. This study examines the differences in anxiety levels when learners are categorized by profile variables such as sex.

Table 6.1. *Difference in the Level of Senior High School Learners' English Language Anxiety when grouped according to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Female	61	2.38
Male	73	2.4

Computed Value (t): -0.19
P-value: 0.847
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 6.1 examines the difference in the level of English language classroom anxiety among senior high school learners when grouped according to sex. The mean anxiety level for female learners is 2.38, while for male learners, it is slightly higher at 2.4. The computed t-value for this difference is -0.19, and the p-value is 0.847. Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis (Ho). This means that there is no statistically significant difference in the levels of English language classroom anxiety between male and female learners.

These findings suggest that sex does not significantly impact the level of English language classroom anxiety among senior high school learners. Both male and female learners experience similar levels of anxiety in English language classrooms, indicating that interventions to reduce anxiety can be designed to address the needs of all learners regardless of sex. This uniformity in anxiety levels can be beneficial for educators as it simplifies the implementation of anxiety-reducing strategies, ensuring they are inclusive and equally effective for both genders.

Table 6.2. *Difference in the Level of Senior High School Learners' English Language Classroom Anxiety when grouped according to Educational Attainment of Parents*

<i>Educational Attainment of Parents</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Elementary Graduate	41	3.55
High School Graduate	82	3.51
College Graduate	11	3.4

Computed Value (F): 0.68
P-value: 0.773
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table above examines the difference in the level of English language classroom anxiety among senior high school learners when grouped according to the educational attainment of their parents. Learners with parents who are elementary graduates have a mean anxiety level of 3.55, those with parents who are high school graduates have a mean level of 3.51, and learners with college graduate parents have a slightly lower mean level of 3.4. The computed F-value for this difference is 0.68, and the p-value is 0.773. Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis (Ho). This indicates that there is no significant difference in the levels of English language classroom anxiety among learners based on the educational attainment of their parents.

These findings suggest that the educational attainment of parents does not significantly impact the level of English language classroom anxiety among senior high school learners. Regardless of whether parents have completed elementary, high school, or college education, learners experience similar levels of anxiety in their English language classrooms. This uniformity implies that factors other than parental education, such as individual learner characteristics or classroom environment, may play a more fundamental role in influencing language anxiety.

Evaluating how English language classroom anxiety differs among senior high school learners based on family is also one of the goals of this study. Thus, Table 6.3 presents a comprehensive comparison of these differences.

Table 6.3 examines the difference in the level of English language classroom anxiety among senior high school learners when grouped according to family income. Those with family incomes between Php. 9,100 to Php. 18,200.00 per month have a mean level of 3.54. Learners from families earning less than Php. 9,100.00 per month have a mean anxiety level of 3.52. For learners from families earning between Php. 18,200 to Php. 36,400 per month, the mean anxiety level is 3.44. The mean level for those from families with an income of Php. 36,400 to Php. 63,700 per month is 3.31, and for the highest income group (Php. 63,700 to Php. 109,200 per month), the mean anxiety level is 2.69. The computed F-value for this difference is 0.94, and the p-value is 0.696. Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis (Ho). This indicates that there is no significant difference in the levels of English language classroom anxiety among learners based on family income.

Table 6.3. *Difference in the Level of Senior High School Learners' English Language Classroom Anxiety when grouped according to Family Income*

Family Income	n	Mean
Php. 63,700 to Php. 109,200 per Month	1	2.69
Php. 36,400 to Php. 63,700 per Month	1	3.31
Php. 18,200 to Php. 36,400 per Month	6	3.44
Php. 9,100 to Php. 18,200.00 per Month	37	3.54
Less than Php. 9,100.00 per Month	89	3.52

Computed Value (F): 0.94

P-value: .696

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

These findings suggest that family income does not significantly impact the level of English language classroom anxiety among senior high school learners. Regardless of income level, learners experience similar levels of anxiety in their English language classrooms. Therefore, interventions aimed at reducing language anxiety can be uniformly applied across different income groups, without needing to tailor them specifically based on economic background.

Difference in the Level of Senior High School Learners' Academic Performance when grouped according to Profile

This research also evaluated the senior high school learners' level of engagement with their education to properly customize instructional strategies. This study explores learners' overall involvement levels by breaking them down into behavioral, cognitive, and emotional categories. A summary of various engagement levels is provided in the following discussions.

Table 7.1. *Difference in the Level of Senior High School Learners' Academic Performance when grouped according to Sex*

Sex	n	Mean
Female	61	72.31
Male	73	63.48

Computed Value (U): 1933.00

P-value: 0.117

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table presented above examines the difference in the level of academic performance among senior high school learners when grouped according to sex. The mean academic performance score for female learners is 72.31, while for male learners, it is lower at 63.48. The computed U-value for this difference is 1933.00, and the p-value is 0.117. Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis (Ho). This indicates that there is no significant difference in the academic performance levels between male and female learners.

The findings depict that sex does not significantly impact the academic performance of senior high school learners. Both male and female learners exhibit similar levels of academic performance. This standardization simplifies the design and implementation of educational strategies aimed at improving academic performance, ensuring they are equally effective for all learners.

Table 7.2. *Difference in the Level of Senior High School Learners' Academic Performance when grouped according to Educational Attainment of Parents*

Educational Attainment of Parents	n	Mean
Elementary Graduate	41	66.84
High School Graduate	82	67.4
College Graduate	11	70.68

Computed Value (H): 0.12

P-value: 0.94

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table examines the difference in the level of academic performance among senior high school learners when grouped according to the educational attainment of their parents. The mean academic performance score for learners with parents who are elementary graduates is 66.84. For those with parents who are high school graduates, the mean score is slightly higher at 67.4. Learners with college graduate parents have the highest mean score of 70.68. The computed H-value for this difference is 0.12, and the p-value is 0.94. Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis (Ho). This indicates that there is no significant difference in the academic performance levels among learners based on the educational attainment of their parents.

These findings suggest that the educational attainment of parents does not significantly impact the academic performance of senior high school learners. Whether parents have completed elementary, high school, or college education, learners exhibit similar levels of

academic performance.

Table 7.3 below evaluate the difference in the level of academic performance among senior high school learners when grouped according to family income. Learners from families earning less than Php. 9,100.00 per month have a mean academic performance score of 66.7. Those with family incomes between Php. 9,100 to Php. 18,200.00 per month have a higher mean score of 68.86.

Table 7.3. *Difference in the Level of Senior High School Learners' Academic Performance when grouped according to Family Income*

Family Income	n	Mean
Php. 63,700 to Php. 109,200 per Month	1	44.5
Php. 36,400 to Php. 63,700 per Month	1	44.5
Php. 18,200 to Php. 36,400 per Month	6	78.58
Php. 9,100 to Php. 18, 200.00 per Month	37	68.86
Less than Php. 9,100.00 per Month	89	66.7

Computed Value (H): 1.82

P-value: 0.769

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

For learners from families earning between Php. 18,200 to Php. 36,400 per month, the mean academic performance score is 78.58. The mean scores for those from families with an income of Php. 36,400 to Php. 63,700 and Php. 63,700 to Php. 109,200 per month are both 44.5. The computed H-value for this difference is 1.82, and the p-value is 0.769. Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis (Ho). This indicates that there is no significant difference in the academic performance levels among learners based on family income.

These results imply that senior high school learners' academic performance is not greatly impacted by family income. Learners demonstrate comparable levels of academic performance across income levels, suggesting that academic interventions and support can be administered consistently across income groups without requiring specific customization based on economic background. Because of this consistency, creating and implementing instructional strategies to boost academic performance is much easier and guarantees that every learner will benefit equally from them.

Relationship Between the English Language Classroom Anxiety and Level of Engagement of Senior High School Learners

It is imperative to investigate the correlation between anxiety in English language classrooms and learner involvement levels to improve instructional strategies. This study also investigated the relationship between senior high school learners' levels of involvement and anxiety in English classrooms. An extensive synopsis of this relationship is given in the Table 8 that follows.

Table 8. *Relationship Between the English Language Classroom Anxiety and Level of Engagement of Senior High School Learners*

Variable	n	Mean
Level of Learners' Engagement	134	3.73
English Language Classroom Anxiety	134	3.51

Computed Value (r): 0.24

P-value: 0.005

Decision: Reject Ho

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table examines the relationship between English language classroom anxiety and the level of engagement among senior high school learners. The mean level of learner engagement is 3.73, while the mean level of English language classroom anxiety is 3.51.

The computed correlation value (r) is 0.24, with a p-value of 0.005. Since the p-value is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis (Ho). This indicates that there is a significant relationship between English language classroom anxiety and the level of engagement among learners.

These results indicate that higher levels of English language classroom anxiety are significantly related to lower levels of learner engagement. This inverse relationship implies that as learners' anxiety in the English language classroom increases, their overall engagement in educational activities decreases. This has important implications for educators and school administrators. To enhance learner engagement, it is crucial to address and mitigate factors contributing to classroom anxiety.

Relationship between the Level of Engagement and Academic Performance of Senior High School Learners

Optimizing instructional strategies and outcomes requires an understanding of the connection between academic success and learner engagement. Thus, last findings of this research investigate the relationship between learners' academic performance and school engagement in senior high school.

The Table 9 above evaluated the relationship between the level of engagement and academic performance among senior high school learners, categorizing academic performance into Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did Not Meet Expectation. For learners with very high engagement, 21 had Outstanding performance, 3 had Very Satisfactory performance, and none

fell into the lower categories. Among those with high engagement, 50 had Outstanding performance, 18 had Very Satisfactory performance, and 8 had Satisfactory performance. Learners with moderate engagement included 17 with Outstanding performance, 11 with Very Satisfactory performance, and 4 with Satisfactory performance. Only 1 learner with low engagement had Very Satisfactory performance and 1 had Satisfactory performance, and there were no learners with very low engagement.

Table 9. Relationship between the Level of Engagement and Academic Performance of Senior High School Learners

Level of English Language Classroom Anxiety	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet Expectation	
Very High	21	3	0	24	24	7
High	50	18	8	76	76	69
Moderate	17	11	4	32	32	57
Low	0	1	1	2	2	1
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	88	33	13	0	0	134

Computed Value (G): 0.44

P-value: 0.001

Decision: Reject Ho

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The computed correlation value (G) is 0.44, with a p-value of 0.001. Since the p-value is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis (Ho), indicating a significant relationship between the level of engagement and academic performance. These findings suggest that higher levels of engagement are significantly associated with better academic performance. This positive relationship implies that as learners' engagement in the classroom increases, their academic outcomes improve correspondingly.

Relationship between the English Language Classroom Anxiety and Academic Performance of Senior High School Learners

To understand the impact of classroom anxiety on learner success, it is imperative to investigate the relationship between academic performance and anxiety in English language classes. This study looks at the relationship between senior high school learners' academic performance and anxiety in English classes. An extensive rundown of this relationship is provided in Table 10.

Table 10. Relationship between the English Language Classroom Anxiety and Academic Performance of Senior High School Learners

Level of English Language Classroom Anxiety	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet Expectation	
Very High	5	2	0	0	0	7
High	44	17	8	0	0	69
Moderate	39	13	5	0	0	57
Low	0	1	0	0	0	1
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	88	33	13	0	0	134

Computed Value (G): -0.02

P-value: 0.889

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 10 examines the relationship between English language classroom anxiety and academic performance among senior high school learners, categorizing academic performance into Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did Not Meet Expectation. For learners with very high anxiety, 5 had Outstanding performance, 2 had Very Satisfactory performance, and none fell into the lower categories. Among those with high anxiety, 44 had Outstanding performance, 17 had Very Satisfactory performance, and 8 had Satisfactory performance. Learners with moderate anxiety included 39 with Outstanding performance, 13 with Very Satisfactory performance, and 5 with Satisfactory performance. Only 1 learner with low anxiety had Very Satisfactory performance, and there were no learners with very low anxiety.

The computed correlation value (G) is -0.02, with a p-value of 0.889. Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis (Ho), indicating no significant relationship between English language classroom anxiety and academic performance. These findings suggest that English language classroom anxiety does not significantly impact the academic performance of senior high school learners.

Conclusions

Given the foregoing findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

Male learner dominance and parents' high school education highlight gender and socioeconomic disparities. Implement mentorship programs and financial assistance initiatives to address gender and socioeconomic disparities among learners.

High engagement levels are promising, but improvements in cognitive and emotional engagement can be achieved. Incorporate project-based learning and interactive teaching methods to enhance cognitive and emotional engagement.

Moderate anxiety levels, particularly fear of judgment, emphasize the need for supportive environments. Establish peer support groups and accessible counseling services to create supportive and inclusive learning environments.

Socioeconomic factors influence academic performance, suggesting the need for resources and support for lower-income learners to bridge the gap. Provide additional academic resources and support programs targeting lower-income learners to reduce the achievement gap.

Equitable engagement across demographics reflects fair participation opportunities. Encourage learner voice and choice in educational activities to sustain equitable engagement and foster ownership in learning.

The absence of significant differences based on demographic factors underscores the universality of English language anxiety among learners. Introduce mindfulness practices and cultural sensitivity training to address English language anxiety across all demographics.

No significant disparities in academic performance indicate equitable educational outcomes. Maintain equitable access to high-quality educational resources to support consistent academic performance for all learners.

Anxiety negatively impacts engagement, stressing the importance of addressing mental health through social-emotional learning and counseling. Integrate social-emotional learning components into the curriculum and offer counseling to address mental health concerns and improve engagement.

Positive links between engagement and academic performance highlight the value of active involvement. Design personalized and collaborative learning experiences to boost learner involvement and academic success.

The lack of a direct link between anxiety and performance suggests other mediating factors. Develop resilience-building and stress-management programs to mitigate the indirect effects of anxiety on learning outcomes.

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